

Multicriteria Decision Analysis for Development Ranking of Balkan Countries

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Abstract—In this research, the Balkan peninsula countries' developmental integration into European Union represents the strategic economic development objectives of the countries in the region. In order to objectively analyze the level of economic development competition of Balkan Peninsula countries, the mathematical compromise programming technique of multicriteria evaluation is used in this ranking problem. The primary aim of this research is to explain the role and significance of the multicriteria method evaluation using a real example for compromise solutions. Using the mathematical compromise programming technique, twelve countries of the Balkan Peninsula are economically evaluated and mutually compared. The economic development evaluation of the countries is performed according to five evaluation criteria forming the basis for economic development evaluation. The multiattribute model is solved using the mathematical compromise programming technique for producing different Pareto solutions. The results obtained by the multicriteria evaluation gives the possibility of identification and evaluation of the most eminent economic development indicators for each country separately. Finally, in this way, the proposed method has proved to be a successful model for the evaluation of the Balkan peninsula countries' economic development competition.

Keywords—Balkan peninsula countries, standard deviation, multicriteria decision making, mathematical compromise programming, multicriteria decision making, multicriteria analysis, multicriteria decision analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN this regional economic development, multicriteria decision making (MCDM) analysis is used to making optimal decisions in the presence of multiple usually conflicting criteria for MCDM problems in real life situations. A typical MCDM problem involves a number of alternatives to be assessed and a number of criteria to evaluate the alternatives for multicriteria compromise optimization of complex systems [1], [2]. MCDM methods use different normalizations and aggregating functions for ranking. In multicriteria compromise optimization data normalization is used to eliminate the units of criterion functions. The multicriteria compromise optimization method determines the compromise ranking and the compromise solution obtained with the given weights of criteria. The multicriteria compromise optimization method focuses on ranking and selecting from a set of alternatives in the presence of conflicting criteria, whilst introducing the multicriteria ranking index based on the particular measure of “closeness” to the “ideal” solution, which originated from the multicriteria compromise programming method. The multicriteria compromise optimization method of compromise ranking determines a quantitative solution, providing a maximum “group utility” for the “majority” and a minimum of an

individual regret for the “opponent” [25], [26], [32]. The multicriteria compromise optimization method also determines a solution with the shortest distance to the ideal solution and the greatest distance from the negative ideal solution [24].

The MCDM analysis is usually carried out in the presence of multiple incommensurable and conflicting decision criteria, different units of measurement values among the criteria, and the presence of quite different alternatives [3]. Therefore, the alternatives in MCDM problem have performance values for all criteria and based on these quantitative values; the alternatives can be assessed and ranked for selection problem in consideration [4], [5]. These computational MCDM methods are widely considered to be significant potential models for analyzing complex system problems due to their inherent ability to rank different alternatives on various criteria for possible selection of the optimal alternative(s) [6], [7]. The MCDM methods are divided into three categories to bring the MCDM methods together according to some similarities: (i) multiattribute methods; (ii) outranking methods; (iii) interactive methods [8], [9]. On the other hand, MCDM methods are classified: (i) unique synthesis criterion method, eliminating any incomparability; (ii) outranking synthesis method, accepting incomparability; (iii) interactive local judgment method, with trial-error interaction [1], [10].

Basically, there are three sequential steps in operating any MCDM method involving numerical analysis of alternatives; determination of the relevant criteria and alternatives, attaching numerical values to the relative importance or priority to critical criteria, and impact of the alternatives on the decision criteria, and processing the numerical values to determine a ranking of each alternative for a compromise solution [2], [11]. Hence, multicriteria MCDM methods are able to improve the quality of decisions by making the decision making process more explicit, rational and efficient for multicriteria compromise optimization analysis. On the other hand, an interesting problem with MCDM methods which rank a set of alternatives in terms of numerous competing criteria is that often different MCDM methods may yield different rank orders when they are applied with the same numerical data [12], [13]. A great deal of effort has been made regarding the multicriteria compromise optimization in ranking problems [18]-[27]. However, a generalized quantitative evaluation model based on multicriteria decision making is still lacking in multiobjective optimization decision making (MODM) problems [1]-[17].

From strategic decision making perspective, determining the most important factors of development ranking is crucial and helps decision makers to focus on factors with the highest weight and identify the best policy to improve the sustainable

development strategy [12]. Therefore, a multicriteria decision making approach is essential in order to evaluate the relative importance of these factors on alternatives. Consequently, this research proposes a model that hybridizes the standard deviation procedure and the mathematical compromise programming technique in order to provide an objective evaluation model that prioritizes the objective weights of development ranking problem. The intended research contributions are: (i) to determine and evaluate the most relevant criteria for development ranking; (ii) to apply a hybrid multicriteria decision model based on standard deviation and multicriteria compromise optimization methodology; (iii) to present results of different MODM analyses that reflects the effects of different criteria on qualitative and quantitative characteristics of the ranking of the alternatives.

Organization of the rest of the paper is as follows: Section II describes the standard deviation approach as an objective weighting procedure in the MCDM models, Section III reviews the MCDM methods, Section IV explains the multicriteria compromise optimization method and vector normalization, and Section V compares the empirical results of a country selection and development ranking problem obtained with the standard deviation - multicriteria compromise optimization model, and Section VI concludes with closing remarks.

II. STANDARD DEVIATION METHOD

Standard deviation procedure is proposed for determining the objective weights of the importance of the attributes. Standard deviation is an objective weighting method in which objective weights are derived from MODM dataset. Weight extraction from MODM datasets is one of the most challenging processes in MCDM models, and standard deviation determines objective criteria weights. Standard deviation is an objective weighting method that assigns an objective weight to each criterion using standard deviations [29]. The deviation of a dataset carries an important information, and it is suitable for comparing the criteria weights after normalizing the MODM dataset.

$$R = [r_{ij}]_{n \times m} = \begin{bmatrix} r_{11} & \cdots & r_{1j} & \cdots & r_{1m} \\ r_{21} & \cdots & r_{2j} & \cdots & r_{2m} \\ \vdots & \cdots & \vdots & \cdots & \vdots \\ r_{n1} & \cdots & r_{nj} & \cdots & r_{nm} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

$$i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m\} \quad j \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$$

where r_{ij} is the performance value of i^{th} alternative on j^{th} criterion, m is the number of alternatives, and n is the number of criteria. Then, the deviation of the j^{th} criterion of i^{th} alternative:

$$\sigma_j = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^m (r_{ij} - \bar{r}_j)^2}{m}} \quad (2)$$

where σ_j is a standard deviation of the data corresponding to the j^{th} attribute. $\bar{r}_j$ is the mean or average value of r_{ij} . The objective weight of the j^{th} attribute can be obtained from the ratio of σ_j to the total deviation of the normalized dataset:

$$\omega_j = \frac{\sigma_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n \sigma_j} \quad (3)$$

where ω_j is the objective weight of the j^{th} criterion that the standard deviation assigns. The standard deviation concept of determining the objective weights of the attributes is comparatively simpler than the entropy method.

III. MULTICRITERIA DECISION MAKING

In this paper, standard deviation and multicriteria compromise optimization, are chosen to deal with the problem of selecting a country with optimal development indices. The multicriteria compromise optimization method reflects a different approach to solving a given discrete MCDM problem of choosing the optimal among several preselected alternatives. The multicriteria compromise optimization method requires the preselection of a countable number of alternatives and the use of a countable number of quantifiable conflicting and incommensurable performance criteria [14], [15].

The evaluation attributes may indicate benefits and costs to a decision maker for an MCDM problem. A larger outcome always means a greater preference for a benefit or less preference for a cost criterion. Hence, after inter- and intra-comparison of the alternatives with respect to a given set of performance attributes, implicit/explicit trade-offs are established and used to rank the alternatives. The problem of ranking countries' development grades is considered as a multicriteria decision making analysis problem. A multicriteria optimization decision analysis procedure, dealing with the various aspects of finding optimum decisions in problems with multiple decision alternatives and conflicting objectives (criteria), recently, has been applied in various fields of technology, economics, mathematics, and computics [16].

In general, in multiobjective optimization, there is no single best solution for MCDM problem in consideration. Therefore, it is common to directly or indirectly search for a set of Pareto efficient solutions, and apply set oriented search procedures for multiobjective optimization analysis [28]. Also, there is an alternative multicriteria optimization approach, which is the construction of ranking and scoring methods that aggregate objectives, which normally yields a particularly efficient solution on the Pareto front. Moreover, in multicriteria decision analysis, the evaluation of multivariate data and trade-offs are discussed, and solution models that can support human decision makers in complex environments [17].

Many MCDM complex problems ranging from production scheduling to online performance evaluation involve selection procedure by ranking alternatives for supporting human decision makers in complex environments [15]. Multicriteria

decision analysis has many applications in decision science, performance science, engineering, and related fields for determining the optimal choice by selecting, classifying or ranking multiple alternatives [15], [16]. There are various MCDM models, applicable to economics, business and related fields, from production to finance, and each has a different capability for determining the best alternative to a set of possible solutions [18].

The configuration of an MCDM model for a decision problem is based upon an abstract language where subjective judgment, intuition, experience, and preference are at the forefront. The main advantage of MCDM models stems from the fact that criteria values of alternatives melt in the same pot for a holistic evaluation, and typically, these models do not require criteria selection or statistical significance tests. The multicriteria compromise optimization method is an MCDM ranking model that converts quantitative ratings of the alternatives into quantitative ranking expressions [19].

optimization computes criteria weights from the MCDM dataset itself, eliminates the issue of consistency due to subjective judgments, and yet continues to benefit from the strength of MCDM analysis process.

IV. MATHEMATICAL COMPROMISE PROGRAMMING

In decision making problems, decision making for MCDM problem is the process of selecting a possible direction of action from all of the available alternatives in the presence of conflicting criteria. On the other hand, the multiplicity of criteria for ranking the alternatives is pervasive, and the decision maker wants to obtain more than one objective or goal in selecting the route of action while satisfying the constraints identified by environment, processes, and resources [20]. The multicriteria compromise optimization method is proposed to solve MCDM problems with conflicting and incommensurable criteria, considering that compromising is acceptable for conflict resolution when the decision maker wants a multicriteria compromise solution that is the nearest to the ideal, and the alternatives are quantitatively evaluated according to identified criteria. The multicriteria compromise optimization approach emphasis on ranking and selecting from a set of alternatives in the presence of conflicting criteria, and proposing compromise solution for MODM problem [21].

The solution of MCDM problems usually starts with a given reference point, and the MCDM problems can then be solved by positioning the alternatives or decisions which are the nearest to the reference point. Therefore, the MCDM problem becomes measuring the distance to the reference point. Goal programming measures this distance by using the weighted sum of absolute distances from given goals. The global criteria method measures this distance by using Minkowski's L_p metric. The L_p metric defines the distance between two points, f_{ij} and f_{ij}^+ (the reference point), in n -dimensional space as

$$L_p = \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^n (f_{ij}^+ - f_{ij})^p \right\}^{1/p} \quad p \geq 1 \quad (4)$$

where L_p the distance ($p=1,2,\dots,\infty$) is operationally significant, when p increases, distance L_p decreases, $L_1 \geq L_2 \geq \dots \geq L_\infty$. Specifically, $p = 1$, L_1 (the Manhattan distance) implies an equal weights for all these deviations and is called, for $p=2$, L_2 (the Euclidean distance) implies that the deviations are weighted proportionately with the largest deviation having the largest weight. Ultimately, while $p = \infty$, L_∞ (the Tchebycheff) implies the largest deviation completely dominates the distance determination.

$$L_\infty = \max_j \{ |f_{ij}^+ - f_{ij}| \} \quad (5)$$

Fig. 1 The overall process of MCDM models

A quantitative MCDM method of multicriteria compromise optimization is proposed to determine the relative rankings of alternatives. The structure of the multicriteria compromise optimization model includes the interacting goal, criteria, and the alternatives. This paper presents an objective ranking method, which embeds vector normalization and standard deviation into multicriteria compromise optimization. The method of standard deviation - multicriteria compromise

Distances L_1 (the Manhattan distance) and L_2 (the Euclidean distance) are the longest and the shortest distances in the geometrical sense; L_∞ (the Tchebycheff) is the shortest distance in the numerical sense.

Especially, considering the incommensurability nature of objectives or criteria, the distance family is then normalized to remove the effects of the incommensurability by using the reference point [18]-[27]. The distance family then becomes

$$L_p = \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^n \left[\frac{(f_{ij}^+ - f_{ij})}{f_{ij}^+} \right]^p \right\}^{1/p} \quad 1 \leq p \leq \infty \quad (6)$$

The amount of L_p decreases when parameter p increases. The technique for order of preference by similarity to ideal solution [24] is proposed to solve multiple attribute decision making (MADM) problems by using the concept of optimum multicriteria compromise solution, and later the concept is further extended for MADM problems, and developed for solving multiple objective decision making (MODM) problems [18]. Thus, using the normalized distance family with the ideal solution being the reference point, the MODM problem becomes solving the following auxiliary problem of aggregating function:

$$\min_{x \in X} L_p^i = \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^n \left[\omega_j \frac{(f_{ij}^+ - f_{ij})}{f_{ij}^+ - f_{ij}^-} \right]^p \right\}^{1/p}$$

$$\min_{x \in X} L_p^i = \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^n \left[\omega_j \frac{(f_{ij}^+(x) - f_{ij}(x))}{f_{ij}^+(x) - f_{ij}^-(x)} \right]^p \right\}^{1/p} \quad 1 \leq p \leq \infty \quad (7)$$

$$L_p^i = \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^n \left[\omega_j \frac{(f_{ij}^+ - f_{ij})}{f_{ij}^+ - f_{ij}^-} \right]^p \right\}^{1/p} \quad p \geq 1$$

$$i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m\} \quad j \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$$

where the distance family is normalized using positive ideal solution (f_{ij}^+) and negative ideal solution (f_{ij}^-) and $p = 1, 2, \dots, \infty$. The value chosen for p reflects the way of achieving a multicriteria compromise solution by minimizing the weighted sum of the deviations of criteria from their respective reference points (ideal solution) [20]-[24].

The measure L_p^i represents the distance of the alternative A_i to the ideal solution, ω_j is the weight of j^{th} objective, f_{ij}^+ is the best (positive ideal solution) value of corresponding j^{th} criterion, and f_{ij}^- is the worst (negative ideal solution) value of corresponding j^{th} criterion. With the concept of optimal compromise solution, the best alternative or decisions of technique for order of preference by similarity to ideal solution

method are those that have the shortest distance from the positive ideal solution as well as have the farthest distance from the negative ideal solution [24]. This multicriteria compromise method assumes that each criterion takes either monotonically increasing or monotonically decreasing utility, the larger the criteria outcome, the greater the preference for beneficial attributes and the less the preference for non beneficial attributes. The multicriteria compromise solution is proposed as a ranking method for decision problems with a predefined decision matrix. The multicriteria compromise solution procedure for ranking alternatives consists of the following main steps:

1. Determine the goal or objective of the problem and identify the relevant decision criteria and alternatives. Construct the decision matrix using all available information on alternatives and criteria. Each row of the decision matrix is allocated to one alternative and each column to one criterion. Therefore, an element x_{ij} of the decision matrix gives the value of j^{th} criterion in original non normalized form and unit for i^{th} alternative.
2. Compute the normalized decision matrix. The normalized value r_{ij} is computed using vector normalization method.

$$r_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij}^2}} \quad \text{for beneficial criteria} \quad (8)$$

$$r_{ij} = 1 - \frac{x_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij}^2}} \quad \text{for non beneficial criteria} \quad (9)$$

3. Compute the weighted normalized decision matrix u_{ij} by multiplying each element of the column of the matrix r_{ij} with its associated weight ω_j . The weighted normalized value u_{ij} is computed.

$$u_{ij} = \omega_j r_{ij} \quad U_i = \sum_{j=1}^n u_{ij} = \sum_{j=1}^n \omega_j r_{ij} \quad (10)$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^n \omega_j = 1 \quad i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m\} \quad j \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$$

where ω_j is the weight of j^{th} objective.

4. Determine the positive ideal and negative ideal solution.

$$A^+ = u_j^+ = \{u_1^+, \dots, u_m^+\} = \left\{ \max_i u_{ij} \mid j \in J, (\min_i u_{ij} \mid j \in J') \right\} \quad (11)$$

$$A^- = u_j^- = \{u_1^-, \dots, u_m^-\} = \left\{ \min_i u_{ij} \mid j \in J, (\max_i u_{ij} \mid j \in J') \right\} \quad (12)$$

where J is associated with benefit criteria, and J' is associated with non beneficial criteria.

5. Compute the separation measures of each alternative from the positive ideal and the negative ideal solutions, using the n dimensional Euclidean geometric distance. The separation of each alternative from the positive ideal solution is given.

$$d_i^+ = \left[\sum_{j=1}^n (u_{ij} - u_j^+)^2 \right]^{1/2} \quad (13)$$

Similarly, the separation from the negative ideal solution is given.

$$d_i^- = \left[\sum_{j=1}^n (u_{ij} - u_j^-)^2 \right]^{1/2} \quad (14)$$

6. Compute the relative closeness coefficient to the positive ideal solution of each alternative. The relative closeness of the alternative A_i with respect to the positive ideal solution d^+ is defined.

$$P_i = \frac{d_i^-}{d_i^+ + d_i^-}, \quad 0 \leq P_i \leq 1 \quad (15)$$

where P_i is the overall performance score for i^{th} alternative. Alternatives, based on the decreasing values of closeness coefficient, are ranked from most valuable to worst using the preference order of alternatives. The best alternative, having highest closeness coefficient P_i is selected.

7. A linear aggregating function Z_i based on the d_i^+ and d_i^- distances is also proposed:

$$Z_i = \alpha d_i^- + (1 - \alpha)(1 - d_i^+) \quad (16)$$

where α is a coefficient that describes the decision maker's decision strategy (aggressive or conservative). The higher α reflects the more conservative the decision maker.

8. Based on the overall performance scores (U_i, P_i, Z_i, S_i) the alternatives are ranked in descending order.

V. EMPIRICAL RESULTS

A. Constructing the Decision Matrix

In this paper, a compromise approach is presented to decision support that applies MCDM methods based on reference points. The MCDM problems start with a decision/evaluation matrix exhibiting the performance of different alternatives with respect to various criteria. A country selection problem is investigated by the mathematical compromise programming technique, and the results are compared with characteristics of the MCDM methods. In order to demonstrate the applicability and potentiality of the multicriteria compromise optimization

method in solving multiobjective decision making problems in sustainable economic growth and development environment, the following quantitative illustrative example is considered. The MCDM dataset of the country selection and ranking problem, for multicriteria decision making in the development ranking of Balkan peninsula countries, consists of twelve alternatives and five identified criteria as given in the decision matrix.

In Table I, Balkan peninsula countries [37] Albania (Al), Bosnia and Herzegovina (Ba), Bulgaria (Bg), Croatia (Hr), Greece (Gr), Kosovo (Ks), Macedonia (Mk), Montenegro (Me), Romania (Ro), Serbia (Rs), Slovenia (Si), and Turkey (Tr) in the rows of the decision matrix are evaluated according to five criteria in the columns of the decision matrix. In this present research work, five attributes for ranking the countries are considered in the decision matrix. Dataset for five criteria was retrieved from world bank database and other related sources [30]-[37] for the year 2017; and these criteria respectively measure GDP per capita, PPP (US\$) (C1), GDP per capita (US\$) (C2), Gini Index (C3), Life Expectancy in years (C4), and Human Development Index (C5). All criteria other than Gini Index (C3) are considered benefit criteria for ranking the alternatives. Standard deviation method is applied to calculate the normalized weights of the criteria. The multicriteria compromise optimization approach is used to determine the most suitable alternative from the obtained values. Table I presents the decision matrix considered in the selection problem.

B. Normalizing the Decision Matrix

The decision matrix in MCDM consideration first requires being normalized so that it becomes dimensionless and all of its elements are comparable. In Table II, application of the proposed methodology starts with the vector normalization as given in (8)-(9).

TABLE I
 DECISION MATRIX OF THE COUNTRY SELECTION PROBLEM

Country	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
Optimization	max	max	min	max	max
Al	12943,46	4537,58	29	73,2	0,714
Ba	13107,72	5148,21	33	77,2	0,750
Bg	20947,99	8227,96	39,1	79,9	0,845
Hr	26288,04	13382,72	32	76,2	0,807
Gr	27601,90	18613,42	36,7	80,1	0,896
Ks	10736,86	3957,44	23,2	77,7	0,786
Mk	15290,31	5414,61	43,2	76,2	0,748
Me	19351,89	7782,84	33,2	76,4	0,807
Ro	26656,77	10817,83	27,3	76,3	0,802
Rs	15428,80	5900,04	29,7	76,5	0,776
Si	34868,21	23597,29	25,6	78,2	0,809
Tr	26518,85	10546,15	40	71,1	0,707
f_j^+	34868,21	23597,29	23,2	80,1	0,896
f_j^-	10736,86	3957,44	43,2	71,1	0,707

The objective weights of criteria are obtained using standard deviation equations (1)-(3) and shown in Table II. The objective weights of identified criteria are computed using standard

deviation and shown in Table II.

TABLE II
 NORMALIZED DECISION MATRIX

Country	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
Optimization	max	max	min	max	max
Weights ω_j	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2
Al	0,00000111	0,00000145	0,99890311	0,00051952	0,04779984
Ba	0,00000116	0,00000167	0,99866701	0,00059301	0,05388822
Bg	0,00000156	0,00000198	0,99834706	0,00060948	0,05868736
Hr	0,00000206	0,00000331	0,99868473	0,00059328	0,05776673
Gr	0,00000243	0,00000505	0,99835291	0,00068564	0,07073230
Ks	0,00000109	0,00000132	0,99881559	0,00074717	0,07105504
Mk	0,00000159	0,00000183	0,99766630	0,00082900	0,07612258
Me	0,00000212	0,00000268	0,99775356	0,00095137	0,09268141
Ro	0,00000317	0,00000388	0,99782898	0,00111174	0,10736925
Rs	0,00000221	0,00000231	0,99732081	0,00134238	0,12018073
Si	0,00000536	0,00000951	0,99725369	0,00172687	0,13811141
Tr	0,00000652	0,00000771	0,99500684	0,00215097	0,12592556
σ_j	0,00000165	0,00000252	0,00102693	0,00049074	0,02965837
ω_j	0,00005289	0,00008067	0,03293524	0,01573889	0,95119231

C. Weighted Normalized Decision Matrix

The normalized decision matrix is weighted using (10) and shown in Table III. The determination of a set of ideal (A_i^+) and negative ideal (A_i^-) solutions are indicated using (11) and (12) as shown in Table III.

The normalized decision matrix is weighted using the mean weight (MW), $w_j = 1/n$, n is the number of criteria. This is based on the assumption that all criteria are of equal importance, and shown in Table IV. The final ranking results are shown in Table VI.

TABLE III
 WEIGHTED NORMALIZED DECISION MATRIX

Country	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
Optimization	max	max	min	max	max
Weights ω_j	0,00005289	0,00008067	0,03293524	0,01573889	0,95119231
Al	0,00000000	0,00000000	0,03289912	0,00000818	0,04546684
Ba	0,00000000	0,00000000	0,03289134	0,00000933	0,05125806
Bg	0,00000000	0,00000000	0,03288080	0,00000959	0,0582297
Hr	0,00000000	0,00000000	0,03289192	0,00000934	0,05494727
Gr	0,00000000	0,00000000	0,03288099	0,00001079	0,06728002
Ks	0,00000000	0,00000000	0,03289623	0,00001176	0,06758700
Mk	0,00000000	0,00000000	0,03285838	0,00001305	0,07240722
Me	0,00000000	0,00000000	0,03286126	0,00001497	0,08815784
Ro	0,00000000	0,00000000	0,03286374	0,00001750	0,10212881
Rs	0,00000000	0,00000000	0,03284700	0,00002113	0,11431499
Si	0,00000000	0,00000000	0,03284479	0,00002718	0,13137051
Tr	0,00000000	0,00000000	0,03277079	0,00003385	0,11977943
u_j^+	0,00000000	0,00000000	0,03277079	0,00003385	0,13137051
u_j^-	0,00000000	0,00000000	0,03289623	0,00000933	0,05125806

D. Computing the Separation Measures

The positive ideal solutions (PIS) d_i^+ and negative ideal solutions (NIS) d_i^- are computed by (13) and (14), and shown in Table V respectively.

TABLE IV
 WEIGHTED NORMALIZED DECISION MATRIX

Country	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
Optimization	max	max	min	max	max
Weights ω_j	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2
Al	0,00000022	0,00000029	0,19978062	0,00010390	0,00955997
Ba	0,00000023	0,00000033	0,19973340	0,00011860	0,01077764
Bg	0,00000031	0,00000040	0,19966941	0,00012190	0,01173747
Hr	0,00000041	0,00000066	0,19973695	0,00011866	0,01155335
Gr	0,00000049	0,00000101	0,19967058	0,00013713	0,01414646
Ks	0,00000022	0,00000026	0,19976312	0,00014943	0,01421101
Mk	0,00000032	0,00000037	0,19953326	0,00016580	0,01522452
Me	0,00000042	0,00000054	0,19955071	0,00019027	0,01853628
Ro	0,00000063	0,00000078	0,19956580	0,00022235	0,02147385
Rs	0,00000044	0,00000046	0,19946416	0,00026848	0,02403615
Si	0,00000107	0,00000190	0,19945074	0,00034537	0,02762228
Tr	0,00000130	0,00000154	0,19900137	0,00043019	0,02518511

E. Computing the Multicriteria Compromise Solutions

In point of fact, in the multicriteria compromise solutions, the evaluation of alternatives according to distances from positive ideal and negative ideal points represents two significant decision attitudes: the distance from positive ideal can be regarded as encouraging aggressive decisions, in which the decision maker tries to approach the best as closely as possible; the distance from negative ideal is conservative, as the decision maker tries to maximize distance to the worst in the Pareto set [34].

Consequently, similar to compromise solution by MCDM methods (regarding α as the weight of the ‘‘majority of criteria’’ strategy, [25], [35], a relative weight for conservative (as opposed to aggressive) decision making can be introduced to aggregate the two distances in multicriteria compromise solution [24]. For instance, the compromise aggregation function (16) uses α as the weight of the conservative decision strategy. Afterwards, conventional aggregation in the multicriteria compromise solution can be regarded as aggregation under a specific value of α . Subsequently, in connection with the country raking problem, the classical aggregation function, (15) is used for integration of distances from positive ideal and negative ideal points, for comparison purposes. The multicriteria compromise solution is stable within a decision making process, which could be the strategy of maximum group utility (when $\alpha > 0.5$ is needed), or ‘‘by consensus’’ $\alpha \approx 0.5$, or ‘‘with veto’’ ($\alpha < 0.5$). Here, α is introduced as the weight of decision making strategy of maximum group utility, here $\alpha = 0.5$. The multicriteria compromise solutions (Z_i) are computed using (13), (14), and (16) with decision strategy α , and final rankings are shown in Table V.

F. Overall Performances of the Alternatives

The performances of the alternatives (U_i , P_i , Z_i and S_i) for MCDM compromise optimization problem are computed using (13)-(16) and shown in Table V and Table VI.

TABLE V
 COMPUTING THE MULTICRITERIA COMPROMISE SOLUTIONS

Alternative	U_i	Rank	d_i^+	d_i^-	P_i	Rank	Z_i	Rank
Al	0,07837413	12	0,08590377	0,00579123	0,06315751	11	0,45994373	12
Ba	0,08415874	11	0,08011254	0,00000489	0,00006108	12	0,45994618	11
Bg	0,08871336	9	0,07554763	0,00456493	0,05698146	9	0,46450865	9
Hr	0,08784853	10	0,07642334	0,00368921	0,04605038	10	0,46363294	10
Gr	0,10017181	8	0,06409059	0,01602197	0,19999319	8	0,47596569	8
Ks	0,10049500	7	0,06378363	0,01632894	0,20382494	7	0,47627265	7
Mk	0,10527865	6	0,05896336	0,02114919	0,26399345	6	0,48109291	6
Me	0,12103407	5	0,04321277	0,03689980	0,46059938	5	0,49684352	5
Ro	0,13501005	4	0,02924185	0,05087076	0,63499062	4	0,51081445	4
Rs	0,14718312	3	0,01705570	0,06305694	0,78710354	3	0,52300062	3
Si	0,16424248	1	0,00007430	0,08011247	0,99907340	1	0,54001908	1
Tr	0,15258407	2	0,01159108	0,06852148	0,85531505	2	0,52846520	2

TABLE VI
 COMPUTING THE MULTICRITERIA COMPROMISE SOLUTIONS

Alternative	S_i	Rank
Al	0,04546684	12
Ba	0,05125806	11
Bg	0,05582297	9
Hr	0,05494727	10
Gr	0,06728002	8
Ks	0,06758700	7
Mk	0,07240722	6
Me	0,08815784	5
Ro	0,10212881	4
Rs	0,11431499	3
Si	0,13137051	1
Tr	0,11977943	2

In Tables V and VI, the final ranking results of the multicriteria compromise optimization method are listed to reflect different ranking characteristics of the multicriteria decision making procedure. The standard deviation based multicriteria compromise optimization method is, objectively, considered for multicriteria compromise optimization for country ranking problem. The objective ranking of country performance values is very useful in operational and strategic management situations. The considered standard deviation based multicriteria compromise optimization method is quite capable in solving real time country selection decision making problems and the rankings of the country alternatives. It is observed that the vector normalization procedure is the most preferred choice to normalize the criteria values in the decision matrices [33].

VI. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

In this paper, to demonstrate the computational flexibility and applicability of multicriteria compromise method, the selection problem of the development ranking of the Balkan peninsula countries is considered, Therefore an efficient MCDM method is proposed to solve the country selection problem and select the best country through a multiple criteria decision making process. In this research, an MDCM approach, multicriteria compromise optimization is implemented to deal with conflicting criteria and a suitable country is selected

successfully. The outranking order of countries and rating of countries can easily be determined by using this method. In multicriteria decision making problems, making the right optimal selection amongst alternatives is an important factor for multicriteria optimization analysis. A country selection problem that ranks sustainable developing indices using multicriteria compromise optimization analysis is quite essential for global sustainable development ranking. Thus, when selecting a developed country from a set of potential prospective states in the present, several criteria and alternatives should be taken into consideration in the course of multicriteria analysis.

In this paper, in a country selection problem with five criteria that are effective in country selection among developed countries, standard deviation and multicriteria compromise optimization are used together for multicriteria optimization analysis problem. The multicriteria compromise optimization technique was applied to optimally select the country process parameters that produced the ranking with the optimum properties. However, standard deviation was used to determine the weights allocated to each value of the development indices utilized in the course of running the multicriteria compromise optimization process. This multiobjective optimization model utilizes a ranking method for the development parameters selection process.

In accordance with the findings of the research, Slovenia is found to be the best optimum performing country according to the evaluation based on the criteria with the proposed multicriteria compromise optimization method. Nevertheless, it should be considered that the results can change if different criteria are used for MCDM country selection problem. Although MCDM plays a significant critical role in many complex real time problems, it is also hard to accept an MCDM method as being accurate all the time for the solution of multiobjective optimization problems. Consequently, it is less likely that the ranking similarities, irregularities, and differences among the applied MCDM methods will take place in multicriteria compromise optimization problems when the considered alternatives are very prominent from each other. Finally, the proposed multicriteria compromise optimization method is considered flexible systematic approach which can

be applied to different types of decision making problems.

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